

Whole Genome Sequences of Cellulose Producing Bacteria with PGP Traits and their Application as Seed Coat Agents to Enhance Plant Growth and Yield

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Abstract

Bacterial cellulose is a natural biopolymer used in various industries due to their tremendous properties i.e. 3D crystalline structure, high water holding capacity, biocompatibility and biodegradability, Therefore, researchers focus to investigate the sustainable ways for cellulose production and their applications. This study investigates cellulose producing bacteria along their credibility as a plant growth promotor, supported by their complete genome sequences obtained through whole-genome shotgun sequencing (WGS), used as a bio-input as the seed coat of Wheat. Various bacterial species were isolated from different fruit samples and screened as cellulose producers and plant growth-promotors. After qualitative and quantitate analysis one *Acetobacter* Sp. BCS2-7401 and three *Bacillus* spp. BCS4-7403, BCS6-7404 and BCS9-7407 were selected and identified as *Acetobacter tropicalis* (BCS2-7401), *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (BCS4-7403), *Bacillus velezensis* (BCS6-7404) and *Bacillus subtilis* (BCS9-7407). The assembled genome of *Acetobacter tropicalis* (BCS2-7401) consist of 4,289,507 bp, distributed in 75 contigs with an N50 value of 228.8kb and 54.8 % GC, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (BCS4-7403) consist of 3,974,689bp, distributed in 41 contigs with an N50 value of 2,032 and 46.5 % GC, and *Bacillus velezensis* (BCS6-7404) consist of 54,154bp, distributed in 33 contigs with an N50 value of 2,133.01 and 46 % GC while *Bacillus subtilis* (BCS9-7407) consist of 4,149,660bp, distributed in 63 contigs with an N50 value of 267 kb and 43 % GC. Primary screening of these strains confirmed the significant production of cellulose with other secondary metabolites, i.e., auxin production, HCN production, phosphate solubilization, indole production, and nitrogen fixation. The analysis of these bacterial genomes and proteome may provide important information on new polysaccharides production and other biomolecules of interests, which could lead to open the door for new kind of applications in polymer and agriculture industry.

Introduction

Bacterial Cellulose (BC) is a natural biomaterial that is produced by various bacterial species i.e. *Acetobacter*, *Gluconobacter*, *Bacillus*, *Pseudomonas*, *yeast and fungi*. It is valuable due to its exceptional properties, water retention capacity, high mechanical strength, and distinctive nanofiber architecture. BC has established itself as a valuable resource in various sectors, such as the textile, polymer, biomedical and agricultural industries (Wang et al., 2025). Its potential applications in agriculture sector are as follows, delivery of bioactive agents, Seed coating material for stress and disease resistance, Super biosorbent and crop cover in the form of mulch. Contemporary agricultural systems encounter the intricate challenge of optimising crop yield and quality, concurrently reducing resource input and environmental impact. The global population is reach approximately 9.5 billion by 2050, highlighting the urgency of the situation. To ensure global food security among these constraints, it is essential to develop advanced agricultural practices that prioritise efficiency and sustainability (Paravar et al., 2023). The urgent need to develop high-performance, cost-effective, and eco-friendly materials has been encouraged by the increasing awareness of environmental sustainability in recent decades. This endeavour has expedited the search for innovative biobased materials, in which bacterial cellulose (BC) has emerged as a promising candidate (Lahiri et al., 2021). Seed coating technology offers a viable approach to tackle these challenges. This technique enhances seed performance, improves germination rates, and increases crop resilience through the application of physical, chemical, or biological agents to seed surfaces. The incorporation of bioactive compounds, such as microbial inoculants, into seed coatings enhances seed handling and sowing precision while providing essential growth-promoting agents directly to the rhizosphere during the initial stages of germination.

In the promotion of plant health and productivity, plant beneficial microorganisms (PBM) are a critical component of these bioactive agents. Various biochemical mechanisms are employed by PBMs to enhance nutrient assimilation, protect against pathogens, and stimulate growth in host plants, thereby establishing mutualistic relationships (Amir et al., 2021). Seed coating with PBM is more targeted and efficient than methods such as foliar sprays or soil inoculation, as it guarantees intimate and early contact between the seedling and beneficial microorganisms (Chirag et al., 2023).

So, the use of seed coating technology, particularly in conjunction with bioinoculants such as PBM and biobased materials such as bacterial cellulose, has the potential to significantly advance sustainable agriculture. It is imperative to conduct ongoing research on the optimisation and molecular comprehension of these systems in order to realise their maximum potential and ensure long-term food security.

Material and Methods

Isolation of bacteria

Fruit samples were gathered from various marketplaces in the Multan area in order to isolate the cellulose producing bacteria. These fruit samples were processed using the method outlined by Saleh et al. (2022). The Hestrin-Scharmm (HS) broth medium was prepared and sterilized in test tubes, inoculated with fruit juices, and then kept at 30°C for seven days. Pellicle formation at the broth's air-liquid interface following incubation was regarded as a favorable outcome, purified these cultures by subsequent streaking and processed for additional qualitative and quantitative screening for cellulose production and plant growth promoting abilities.

Genomic DNA sequences of bacteria

Genomic DNA sequences from the isolates were acquired via MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK; <https://microbesng.com>). Libraries were constructed utilizing the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) with changes, such as doubling the input DNA and prolonging the PCR elongation duration to 45 seconds. The Hamilton Microlab STAR system (Hamilton Bonaduz AG, Switzerland) was utilised for the automation of DNA measurement and library construction. Sequencing was conducted using an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) employing a 250 bp paired-end technique. The sequences were trimmed with Trimmomatic v0.30 (Bolger et al., 2014) employing a sliding window quality threshold of Q15, assembled de novo using SPAdes v3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012), and annotated with Prokka v1.11 (Seemann, 2014).

Taxonomic nomenclature of selected strains

The classification and identification of selected bacterial strains (BCS2-7401, BCS4-7403, BCS6-7404 and BCS9-7407) was determined by using Average Nucleotide Identity calculator (ANI) (<https://www.ezbiocloud.net/tools/ani>). We calculate the OrthoANIu percentage between each strain and reference strain as follows: *Acetobacter tropicalis* reference genome ASM3064446v1 (RefSeq: GCF_030644465.1), *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* reference genome (RefSeq: GCF_046573265.1), *Bacillus velezensis* reference genome ASM4791574v1 (RefSeq: GCF_047915745.1) and *Bacillus subtilis* reference genome ASM4760798v1 (RefSeq: GCF_047607985.1). The taxonomic nomenclature was confirmed by the PubMLST website (<https://pubmlst.org/species-id>).

Results

Genomic features of cellulose producing bacteria

On the basis of cellulose production efficiency and PGP traits following bacterial strains BCS2-7401, BCS4-7403, BCS6-7404 and BCS9-7407 were selected and explore their genomes. The assembled genome of *Acetobacter tropicalis* (BCS2-7401) consist of 4,289,507 bp, distributed in 75 contigs with an N50 value of 228.8kb and 54.8 % GC, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens* (BCS4-7403) consist of 3,974,689bp, distributed in 41 contigs with an N50 value of 2,032 and 46.5 % GC, and

Bacillus velezensis (BCS6-7404) consist of 54,154bp, distributed in 33 contigs with an N50 value of 2,133.01 and 46 % GC while *Bacillus subtilis* (BCS9-7407) consist of 4,149,660bp, distributed in 63 contigs with an N50 value of 267 kb and 43 % GC. A summary of genomic features of selected bacteria is listed in table 1.

Taxonomic classification of cellulose producing bacteria

Taxonomic nomenclature of selected bacterial strains BCS2-7401, BCS4-7403, BCS6-7404 and BCS9-7407 showed ANI values as 92.54% , 94.17%,97.79% and 98.52% which identified the species as *Acetobacter tropicalis*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, *Bacillus velezensis*, *Bacillus subtilis* respectively while the ribosomal sequence identity of all these species was 100% showed in table 2.

Statement of continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to their formal publication and should be regarded as preliminary. We value and invite feedback from the community. Please contact with me at (shumaila.shakeel124@gmail.com) for additional information.

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Table 1: Genomic features of cellulose producing bacteria

Genomic features of bacterial strains	<i>Acetobacter tropicalis</i>	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
Strain ID	BCS2-7401	BCS4-7403	BCS6-7404	BCS9-7407
Total size of genome	4,289,507	3,974,689	54,154	4,149,660
Number of reads	844,228	490,951	1,030,925	1,030,93
Number of contigs	75	41	33	63
N50	228,838	2,032,220	2,133,008	267,003
GC %	54.8	46.5	46	43
Genome coverage	42x	45x	50x	42x
Protein coding gene	3,732	3,786	3,929	4,206
tRNA number	48	116	108	84
ncRNA number	4	5	5	5
Bio project	PRJNA1204098	PRJNA1204098	PRJNA1204098	PRJNA1204098
Biosample	SAMN46011644	SAMN46041534	SAMN46078646	SAMN46189538
Accession (Genbank)	JBKGFQ000000000	JBKICE000000000	JBLRML000000000	JBLKPR000000000
Accession (assembly)	GCA_046519855.1	GCA_046573265.1	GCA_047915745.1	GCA_047607985.1

Table 2: Taxonomic features of cellulose producing bacteria predicted by MLST

Predicted Taxa of Selected strains by using MLST				Ribosomal MLST			
Bacterial strains	Rank	Taxon	Support	Taxonomy	rST	Genus	Specie
BCS2-7401	Species	<i>Acetobacter tropicalis</i>	100%	<i>Pseudomonadota>Alphaproteobacteria>Acetobacterales>Acetobacteraceae>Acetobacter> Acetobacter tropicalis</i>	844,228	<i>Acetobacter</i>	<i>Acetobacter tropicalis</i>
BCS4-7403	Species	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota>Bacilli>Bacillales>Bacillaceae>Bacillus>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>	193,826	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus amyloliquefaciens</i>
BCS6-7404	Species	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota>Bacilli>Bacillales>Bacillaceae>Bacillus>Bacillus velezensis</i>	1,388,89	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus velezensis</i>
BCS9-7407	Species	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	100%	<i>Bacillota>Bacilli>Bacillales>Bacillaceae>Bacillus>Bacillus subtilis</i>	1,030,92	<i>Bacillus</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>

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